

THE IMPACT OF DEGRADATION PROCESSES IN THE MAGNETIC CORE, WINDINGS, AND INSULATION OF OIL-IMMERSED POWER TRANSFORMERS ON ENERGY LOSSES

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This article analyzes the factors affecting the energy efficiency of oil-immersed power transformers in power grids that have expired their service life. The long-term operation of transformers, the variability of the load and the quality of repair have been scientifically analyzed as factors directly influencing the energy efficiency of transformers.

Key words: oil power transformer, energy efficiency, energy waste, degradation, waste, capital repair

Introduction

All the countries in the world have their own power supply system. Depending on the technical characteristics of the technology and technological equipment used in these systems, the percentage of losses in relation to the generated and transmitted electricity is different. These figures are 5-8% in developed countries of Europe and Asia, and 10-16% in Russia, Central Asia and Arab countries [1]. The current economic situation in all countries does not allow for a complete replacement of power transformer complexes [2]. Therefore, maintaining the level of reliable operation of obsolete electrical equipment is one of the most important tasks of the direction of electrical power systems and complexes at the current stage.

Materials and Methods

60% of oil-immersed power transformers used in power grids have experienced a long period of operation. During this period, transformers have been repaired several times, sometimes dozens of times, and despite the increase in the population, the capacity of existing transformers in the regions has not been

increased or some consumers have not been separately isolated. As a result, transformers have overheated, hysteresis losses in magnetic core materials have increased, dielectric materials have aged, the risk of insulation breakdown has increased, and deformations in the magnetic core have been observed due to operators' negligence during repair processes (Figure 1.1) [10].

Figure 1.1. Deformations that occurred in the magnetic core during the repair process of the transformer

The efficiency and reliability of oil power transformers directly depends on the serviceability of their components. During operation, transformer elements (magnetic core, winding, insulating oil, etc.) are subject to varying degrees of degradation as a result of physicochemical, electromagnetic and mechanical effects. As a result of this degradation, changes occur in the electrical, thermal and mechanical parameters of the transformer, which, first of all, leads to an increase in energy waste [1,3].

The following three main parameters were considered in the transformer degradation:

- ✓ ☐ Magnetic core degradation (δFe);
- ✓ ☐ winding degradation (δW);
- ✓ ☐ insulation and oil degradation (δO).

The effect of these parts on the power dissipation of an oil-immersed power transformer was considered as follows:

1. Magnetic core degradation (δFe):

As a result of the degradation of the magnetic core, the insulation of the steel sheets is damaged, which leads to an increase in eddy currents in the steel plates of the magnetic core. As a result, the magnetic bonds are broken, the surface area of the hysteresis loop increases, the magnetic interaction decreases, and the magnetic induction (B_m) decreases. The hysteresis constant k_{gis} (depending on the core material) and k_{uyur} (the eddy current constant) increase [4,5]. Therefore, for both dissipation components, we introduce coefficients in the form of δFe

$$:\Delta W_{SI} = \Delta P_{SI,n} \cdot \left(\frac{U_i}{U_{YK}}\right)^2 T \cdot (1 + \alpha_{Fe} \cdot \delta_{Fe}(t)) \quad (1)$$

where, α_{Fe} – is the coefficient of magnetic core degradation affecting energy dissipation ($\alpha_{Fe} > 0$);

$\delta_{Fe}(t)$ – is the time-dependent degradation rate in the range ($0 \leq \delta_{Fe} \leq 1$).

The relative increase in energy losses in the magnetic core of oil-immersed power transformers is determined as follows::

$$\alpha_{Fe} = \frac{P_{Fe,max} - P_{Fe,0}}{P_{Fe,0}} \quad (2)$$

where, $P_{Fe,max}$ – maximum (critical degradation) energy loss in the magnetic core;

$P_{Fe,0}$ – y energy loss in a new magnetic core.

The energy losses of a magnetic core consist of two components: hysteresis and eddy current losses, each of which has its own coefficient, determined by expression (3) [5,6]:

$$P_{Fe} = k_{gis} \cdot f \cdot B_m^n \cdot V_{Fe} + k_{uyur} \cdot f^2 \cdot B_m^2 \cdot t^2 \cdot \frac{V_{Fe}}{\rho_{Fe}} \quad (3)$$

As a result of degradation, k_{gis} and k_{uyur} change as follows:

$$k_{gis} = k_{gis,0} \cdot (1 + \beta_{gis} \cdot \delta_{Fe}) \quad (4)$$

$$k_{uyur} = k_{uyur,0} \cdot (1 + \beta_{gis} \cdot \delta_{Fe}) \quad (5)$$

bwhere, β_{gis} va β_{uyur} – are the degradation sensitivity coefficients of hysteresis and cumulative current constant, respectively ($\beta_{gis} \approx 0,08 - 0,25$, $\beta_{uyur} \approx 0,10 - 0,35$).

The relative increase in energy losses in the magnetic core of oil-immersed power transformers (α_{Fe}) can be expressed in the general case as follows [5,6]:

$$\alpha_{Fe} = \frac{k_{gis} \cdot \beta_{gis} \cdot P_{gis,0} + k_{uyur} \cdot \beta_{uyur} \cdot P_{uyur,0}}{P_{gis,0} + P_{uyur,0}} \quad (6)$$

where: $P_{gis,0}$ – is the initial hysteresis loss,, $P_{uyur,0}$ – is the initial cumulative current loss.

If several factors (heat, humidity, mechanical vibration, oxidation) act together, they are integrated in the form of product and sum.

Based on the Arrhenius and exponential degradation models, it is expressed as

$$\delta_{Fe}(t) = 1 - \exp\left[- \int_0^t (k_T \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R \cdot T_{Fe}(\tau)}\right) + k_H \cdot H_{Fe}(\tau) + k_M \cdot M_{Fe}(\tau)) d\tau\right] \quad (7)$$

where, k_T , k_H , k_M – degradation sensitivity coefficients for temperature, humidity and mechanical loading.

These sensitivity coefficients are described as follows:

a). Temperature (k_T) degradation sensitivity coefficient [6]. We can divide the degradation by temperature into the following levels:

At low temperatures $k_T = 0,05 \div 0,15$ (year^{-1}) (slow aging), at high temperatures $k_T = 0,1 \div 0,5$ (year^{-1}) (rapid aging, for example, 90 – 110°C), if there is a heat “source”, that is, the main influencing factor is temperature - 3 – 10% degradation is observed per year. k_T usually varies in the range of 0.1÷1.0. E_a (awakening energy) 80–140 kJ/mol.

b). The coefficient of degradation sensitivity to humidity (k_H) is a factor that assesses the effect of humidity on the deterioration (degradation) of the insulation of oil-immersed power transformers [8]. The coefficient of moisture sensitivity (k_H) for electrical insulators, dry and liquid insulation systems is $k_H = 0,02 - 0,08$ (year^{-1}), rarely reaching 0.1. Increasing humidity exponentially increases the degradation rate of dry and liquid insulation. If the humidity increases by 2 times, the degradation rate can increase by 1.5 - 2.0 times [8].

c). Degradation sensitivity coefficient for mechanical loading (k_M): The degradation coefficient for mechanical loading, vibration and short-circuit shocks is $k_M = 0,01 - 0,05$ (year^{-1}), and for severe operating conditions $k_M = 0,07 - 0,1$. If the vibration is strong, the degradation coefficient for mechanical loading (k_M) will be higher. $H_{Fe}(\tau)$, $M_{Fe}(\tau)$ are the time-dependent functions of humidity and mechanical loading, respectively [7,8].

If the humidity changes over time, then the integral value is determined by the expression (8):

$$H_{Fe.avg} = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t \frac{W_{Fe}(\tau)}{W_{Fe.max}} d\tau \quad (8)$$

If the moisture diffusion model (for example, moisture absorption into paper) and Fick's law are used, it is determined by the expression (9):

$$W_{Fe}(\tau) = W_{tash} \cdot (1 - e^{-D\tau/d^2}) \quad (9)$$

where, W_{tash} - is the humidity in the external environment, D - is the diffusion coefficient, d - is the insulation thickness, mm, τ - is time, hours.

The mechanical load action function $M_{Fe}(\tau)$ represents the mechanical load and vibration (e.g., short-circuit shock, operational vibration, external mechanical effects, etc.) acting on the transformer or its magnetic core components over time. When the impulse loads resulting from vibration and short-circuit are high, the mechanical loads lead to faster degradation of the transformer core material [8, 9]

If the load is constant (for example, the same vibration or load is present throughout the entire operation), then

$$W_{Fe}(\tau) = W_0 \quad (10)$$

where, W_0 - is the average mechanical load (for example, vibration acceleration m/s^2 , mechanical load MPa or number of short-circuit shocks).

If the load changes at each time instant, then:

$$W_{Fe}(\tau) = S_{Fe}(\tau) \quad (11)$$

where: $S_{Fe}(\tau)$ - is the mechanical load or vibration at time τ (e.g., measured hourly, daily) [9].

Excessive loading accelerates degradation, so the loading is evaluated relative to a critical limit:

$$M_{Fe}(\tau) = \frac{S_{Fe}(\tau)}{S_{Fe,max}} \quad (12)$$

where $S_{Fe,max}$ is the maximum permissible or critical mechanical load for oil-immersed power transformers (for example, 10 m/s² or 80 MPa, etc.). If $M_{Fe}(\tau) \geq 1$, i.e. the mechanical load at time τ is greater than the maximum permissible mechanical load $S_{Fe}(\tau)$, this means that the transformer has entered the dangerous damage zone.

2. Degradation of the coil (δW):

Degradation occurs in the coil under the influence of physicochemical and electromagnetic processes. Therefore, an integration coefficient is introduced for both waste components in the form of δFe :

$$\Delta W_{SI} = \Delta P_{SI,n} \cdot \left(\frac{U_i}{U_{YK}} \right)^2 \cdot T_{eks} \cdot (1 + \alpha_{Fe} \cdot \delta_{Fe}(t)) \cdot (1 + \alpha_w \cdot \delta_w(t)) \quad (13)$$

The following effects were taken into account.

- Thermal effects: The insulation and varnish layer of the conductor of the cable deteriorate under the influence of temperature.
- Moisture and oxidation: Moisture penetrates the insulation layer, causing its dielectric properties to deteriorate.
- Mechanical loads: Weak contact, short circuit, change in the position of the wires due to vibration, microdisplacements.
- Resistance increase: Conductivity decreases as a result of oxidation in the conductor or contacts.
- Corrosion processes: Rusting, the effect of chemicals [11].

Based on the Arrhenius and exponential degradation models, the expression for determining the degradation of the slag is written as follows [2,9].

$$\delta W(t) = 1 - \exp\left[- \int_0^t (k_{T,W} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a,W}}{R \cdot T_W(\tau)}\right) + k_{H,W} \cdot H_W(\tau) + k_{M,W} \cdot M_W(\tau)) d\tau\right] \quad (14)$$

where, $k_{T,W}$, $k_{H,W}$, $k_{M,W}$ are the sensitivity coefficients of the degradation of the substrate for temperature, humidity and mechanical load; $E_{a,W}$ is the excitation energy of the substrate material; $T_W(\tau)$ is the substrate temperature; $H_W(\tau)$, $M_W(\tau)$ are the time-dependent functions of humidity and mechanical load.

For insulation and varnish material: $k_{T,W} = 0,07 - 0,15$ (year⁻¹), at high temperatures (110 – 120 °C) $k_{T,W} = 0,15$, $W = 0.15 - 0.4$. If there is a heat source, degradation can increase by 5-12 percent per year.

Humidity degradation sensitivity coefficients $k_{H.W} = 0,02 - 0,08$ (year^{-1}), If the humidity increases by 2 times, the degradation rate increases by 1.5–2 times.

For mechanical loads, short circuits, vibrations, shocks, $k_{M.W} = 0.01-0.05$ (year^{-1}), up to 0.08 in heavy duty.

3. Insulation and oil degradation (δ_0):

As a result of insulation and oil degradation, the dielectric properties of the oil and insulating material (conductivity, resistance, $\tan\delta$, gas formation, oxidation) change. The moisture and oxygen content increases, acids, metals and gases are formed. As a result of dielectric properties, ionization, oxidation and hydrolysis reactions, heat and dielectric losses (P_{diel}) increase. As a result, heat and dielectric losses in the insulation and oil increase in the no-load operation mode. By introducing a coefficient for insulation and oil degradation losses, the following expression is obtained [1]-[4]:

$$\Delta W_{SI} = \Delta P_{SI,n} \cdot \left(\frac{U_i}{U_{YK}}\right)^2 \cdot T_{eks} \cdot (1 + \alpha_{Fe} \cdot \delta_{Fe}(t)) \cdot (1 + \alpha_w \cdot \delta_w(t)) \cdot (1 + \alpha_0 \cdot \delta_0(t)) \quad (15)$$

where α_0 is the coefficient of influence of insulation and oil degradation on energy losses ($\alpha_0 > 0$); $\delta_0(t)$ – is the degree of insulation and oil degradation depending on time ($0 \leq \delta_0(t) \leq 1$).

Dielectric loss is mainly dependent on $\tan\delta$ (dissipation tangent) and insulation resistance. As a result of degradation, $\tan\delta$ increases.

$$\tan\delta = (\tan \delta)_0 \cdot (1 + \beta_0 \cdot \delta_0) \quad (16)$$

Where, β_0 is the degradation sensitivity coefficient of $\tan\delta$ ($\beta_0 \approx 0,15 \dots 0,3$).

The mathematical expression for complex degradation (Arrhenius and exponential) can be written as follows for this case [3,10]:

$$\delta_0(t) = 1 - \exp\left[- \int_0^t (k_{T.O} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a.O}}{R \cdot T_0(\tau)}\right) + k_{H.O} \cdot H_0(\tau) + k_{C.O} \cdot C_0(\tau)) d\tau\right] \quad (17)$$

where, $k_{T.O}$, $k_{H.O}$, $k_{C.O}$ are the sensitivity coefficients of temperature, humidity and chemical oxidation degradation, respectively; $E_{a.O}$ is the activation energy (J/mol); $T_0(\tau)$ is the insulation or oil temperature (K); $H_0(\tau)$ is the moisture in the oil or insulation (ppm or %); $C_0(\tau)$ is the oxidation or gas concentration (mg/l, ppm).

a) Temperature $k_{T.O}$ degradation sensitivity coefficient. In dielectric and oil materials $k_{T.O} = 0.07-0.20$ (year^{-1}). At high temperatures $k_{T.O} = 0.15-0.50$ (for example, 90-110°C). If the heat source is strong, the degradation will accelerate.

b) Humidity $k_{H.O}$ degradation sensitivity coefficient. Humidity sensitivity $k_{H.O} = 0.02 - 0.08$ (year^{-1}). If the humidity increases by 2 times, the degradation rate increases by 1.5–2 times.

c) Oxidation $k_{C.O}$ degradation sensitivity coefficient: $k_{C.O} = 0.02-0.07$ (year^{-1}), depending on the situation.

(18) introduced the coefficient k_{deg} , which determines the transformer degradation

$$k_{deg} = (1 + \alpha_{Fe} \cdot \delta_{Fe}(t)) \cdot (1 + \alpha_w \cdot \delta_w(t)) \cdot (1 + \alpha_o \cdot \delta_o(t)) = k_1 k_2 k_3 \quad (18)$$

Conclusion

The study presents an improved mathematical model for determining the value of energy losses in the no-load operation mode of oil-immersed power transformers under long-term service conditions. The model incorporates the transformer degradation coefficient, which comprehensively accounts for the degradation of individual components: magnetic core degradation (δ_{Fe}), winding degradation (δ_w), and insulation and oil degradation (δ_o). This approach makes it possible to more accurately evaluate the effect of aging processes on transformer energy efficiency and provides a scientific basis for optimizing maintenance and repair strategies.

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